

Supplementary file 2

In this supplement, we describe examples of genes and diseases that have been assessed using the framework. We provide a standardized template for assessment that follows the three areas of consideration outlined in the framework (at the end). Examples are grouped by generalized therapy assessment considerations and individualized therapy assessment. We aimed to provide a variety of examples covering different inheritance patterns and pathomechanisms. We also included diseases with existing evidence for successful genetic interventions, as well as those that appear to be promising candidates, to highlight the application of the guidelines. Below, we provide an overview of all discussed diseases. For each example, we provide a brief explanation as to why it was included.

Overview example cases

Generalized Approaches	Individualized Approaches
Spinal muscular atrophy Angelman syndrome Dravet syndrome Stargardt disease SCN2A-associated early infantile epilepsy CSPSD – Cataracts, spastic paraparesis, and speech delay Osteogenesis imperfecta	NEDAMSS (Neurodevelopmental Disorder with Regression, Abnormal Movements, Loss of Speech, and Seizures) Niemann Pick disease type C GM1 gangliosidosis Leigh syndrome, Mitochondrial complex I deficiency, nuclear type 34 Lissencephaly 1 Marfan syndrome Dejerine-Sottas disease

Generalized Approaches

Spinal Muscular Atrophy

We discuss spinal muscular atrophy as a prime example of a disease for which a genetic intervention is clinically beneficial, and where therapeutic success of multiple different targeted therapies has clinically been proven in the past decade.

Disease	SMA type 1	OMIM	# 253300	Orphanet	140468
Gene	SMN1	GeneReviews	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1352/		
Molecular Criteria					
Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)	SMA is caused by biallelic LoF variants in <i>SMN1</i> , with >95% variants of large genomic deletion. A second gene - <i>SMN2</i> – is almost identical to <i>SMN1</i> and produces SMN protein, albeit at much reduced levels due to a genetic variation which affects the pre-mRNA splicing of <i>SMN2</i> exon 7. <i>SMN2</i> exists in multiple copies, and the number of copies modifies the phenotype and disease severity in SMA patients. ¹ Here, we evaluate SMA type 1.				
Inheritance + Pathomechanism	Autosomal recessive LoF				
Dosage sensitivity	Suspected sensitivity for high SMN doses. ²				
Therapeutic Approach	Upregulation via gene replacement or via the <i>SMN2</i> copy allele. In general, gene editing is not a suitable option as the most common variants are larger deletions that cannot be edited.				
Clinical Criteria					
Natural History Data	Well-described disease across all SMA types that are associated with the number of <i>SMN2</i> copies with plenty of natural history data.				
Symptoms + Outcome measures	Muscle weakness and atrophy secondary to loss of motor neurons. Preventing the loss of these motor neurons in the spinal cord with genetic therapy can also prevent the development of muscle phenotypes. Outcome measures include the halt of progression or gain of developmental milestones.				
Progression rate + Therapeutic Window	Progression rates depend on the SMA type. SMA type 1 is a rapidly progressive disease that, left untreated, leads to death during childhood (before age of 2 years). Narrow window of opportunity for these children.				
Affected tissue + Target tissues	Multisystemic disorder, main manifestation caused by degeneration of the lower motor neurons, target tissue is the spinal cord.				
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk	Severe disease manifestation with death in early childhood (SMA 1), which justifies development of genetic therapy despite potential side effects.				
Practical Criteria					
Available targeted therapies	Spinraza (nusinersen) – antisense oligonucleotide Zolgensma (onasemnogene abeparvovec-xioi) – gene replacement therapy Evrysdi (risdiplam) – small molecule, splicing modulator				
Preclinical development necessities	Multiple mouse models for different SMA types are available, as well as cellular models like iPSC-derived moto neurons.				
Individualized vs. Generalized	Given the number of patients born with the disease every year, as well as the narrow temporal window of opportunity, a generalized approach is recommended.				
Outcome					

Suitable for generalized genetic therapy development.
 SMA is a prime example of a severely debilitating and progressive genetic disease affecting the nervous system. There is a narrow therapeutic window for type 1, which is why the disease is better suited for a generalized therapeutic approach. Given its unique genetics (*SMN1* and pseudogene *SMN2*), there were multiple opportunities to develop distinct genetic therapies, all with the aim of enhancing SMN protein levels.

Angelman syndrome

Angelman syndrome is discussed as a well-known disease for which a therapeutic intervention is suitable on the molecular level. No therapy has yet been market-approved, but several clinical trials are ongoing.

Disease	Angelman Syndrome	OMIM	# 105830	Orphanet	72
Gene	UBE3A	GeneReviews	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1144/		
Molecular Criteria					
Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)	Angelman syndrome (AS) is caused by loss of maternal <i>UBE3A</i> expression. Most often caused by maternal deletions of chromosome 15q11.2-q13. However, paternal uniparental disomy, imprinting defects, or pathogenic variants in the maternal <i>UBE3A</i> gene can also be the molecular genetic diagnosis. Although a large part of the phenotypes is shared, some phenotypes and the severity of phenotypes depend on the molecular genetic causes of Angelman syndrome. The penetrance of genetic defects depends on which allele contains the defect, as the paternal allele is silenced in neurons, the primary affected cell type.				
Inheritance + Pathomechanism	Autosomal dominant LoF				
Dosage sensitivity	The minimal required <i>UBE3A</i> expression is not known. However, increased levels of <i>UBE3A</i> expression are suspected to contribute to the phenotypes associated with dup15q syndrome. ³				
Therapeutic Approach	Upregulation via unsilencing of the WT allele.				
Clinical Criteria					
Natural History Data	There is extensive natural history data available.				
Symptoms + Outcome measures	Severe developmental delay and intellectual disability, severe speech impairment, and a happy demeanor. Microcephaly and seizures are also common. Outcome measures are normalization of an abnormal EEG and developmental improvement. ⁴				
Progression rate + Therapeutic Window	There is no progression rate. However, although the therapeutic window has not yet been defined, pre-clinical studies suggest that the therapeutic window is during childhood, which will close due to the missed developmental milestones. ⁵				
Affected tissue + Target tissues	Both the primary affected and target tissue is brain, requiring targeting neurons specifically.				
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk	The severe clinical manifestation warranted therapeutic development				
Practical Criteria					
Available targeted therapies	Multiple therapies are currently in clinical trials, including a small molecule drug ercanetide (NNZ-2591) and multiple antisense oligonucleotides (ION582, GTX-102, and Rugonersen).				
Preclinical development necessities	Multiple mouse models and human stem cell models are available for preclinical testing.				

Individualized vs. Generalized	Given the prevalence and the window of opportunity, a generalized therapeutic approach is recommended.
Outcome	
Suitable for genetic therapy development. Angelman syndrome is a good example of a severely debilitating neurodevelopmental disorder. Due to the imprinting in the genomic region, development of generalized therapeutic approaches that unsilence the paternal allele is possible, with the aim of increasing UBE3A protein levels.	

Dravet Syndrome

Dravet syndrome is listed as an example since it is another well-known disorder for which a genetic intervention has previously been deemed suitable and for which different therapeutic strategies are currently under development.

Disease	Dravet Syndrome	OMIM	# 607208	Orphanet	33069
Gene	SCN1A	GeneReviews	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1318/		
Molecular Criteria					
Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)	Dravet syndrome, a development and epileptic encephalopathy, is caused by heterozygous LoF variants in <i>SCN1A</i> that predominantly occur <i>de novo</i> .				
Inheritance + Pathomechanism	Autosomal dominant LoF Off note, GoF variants are also associated with the <i>SCN1A</i> gene, however, lead to a different clinical presentation and are thus not the classical Dravet syndrome.				
Dosage sensitivity	<i>SCN1A</i> is also associated with GoF variants, thus too high doses of the gene product can also cause disease. ⁶				
Therapeutic Approach	Gene replacement or WT upregulation using ASOs.				
Clinical Criteria					
Natural History Data	Sufficient natural history data available				
Symptoms + Outcome measures	Severe developmental and epileptic encephalopathy. Dravet syndrome is a progressive disorder with seizure onset in the first year of life. Patients typically develop normally during the first year; however, cognitive decline occurs as seizures evolve with age. The seizures are usually poorly controlled by state-of-the-art anti-seizure medication (drug-resistant epilepsy). Clinical outcome measures that can be defined are the epileptogenic presentation (severity, duration, frequency of seizures), but also the developmental milestones reached.				
Progression rate + Therapeutic Window	Symptoms associated with Dravet syndrome can worsen over time and patients can lose cognitive function.				
Affected tissue + Target tissues	Primary affected and target tissue is the brain.				
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk	Given the severely debilitating and progressive nature of the disease, a strong therapeutic benefit is expected.				
Practical Criteria					

Available targeted therapies	No genetic therapies have yet been market-approved, but different therapeutic strategies are already under development, such as a gene replacement approach and an ASO strategy to upregulate gene expression from the healthy WT allele. Both therapeutic strategies have been evaluated pre-clinically with success, ^{7,8} and there is a clinical phase 3 trial currently ongoing to upregulate WT <i>SCN1A</i> by poison exon skipping. ⁹
Preclinical development necessities	Several animal (mouse) models and iPSC-derived neuronal culture models are available. ¹⁰
Individualized vs. Generalized	Generalized approach since there are therapeutic possibilities that can target all LoF variants.
Outcome	
<i>SCN1A</i> -associated Dravet syndrome is suitable for genetic therapy development. The severity of the disorder as well as the single target tissue (brain) and the possibility of multiple therapeutic approaches justifies the development and administration of genetic therapy.	

Stargardt Disease

Stargardt disease is included as it is a known disease suitable for therapeutic intervention with different treatment modalities. Since the target tissue is the retina, this is a valuable example to discuss.

Disease	Stargardt Disease	OMIM	# 248200	Orphanet	827
Gene	<i>ABCA4</i>	GeneReviews	n/a		
Molecular Criteria					
Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)	Autosomal recessive variants within the gene <i>ABCA4</i> cause a juvenile macular dystrophy known as Stargardt disease, one of the most common causes of inherited retinal diseases. There is sufficient understanding of the pathomechanism of the disease. The <i>ABCA4</i> gene encodes the rim protein (RmP), which is involved in vitamin A metabolism in photoreceptor cells. When RmP is defective, these byproducts form N-retinylidene-N-retinyl-ethanolamine, a major component of lipofuscin that accumulates in retinal pigment epithelium cells. Excess lipofuscin impairs epithelium function and causes photoreceptor degeneration, seen clinically as retinal flecks and progressive thinning of the outer retinal layers. ¹¹				
Inheritance + Pathomechanism	Autosomal recessive LoF variants				
Dosage sensitivity	Sensitive to biallelic loss of function, no triplosensitivity reported				
Therapeutic Approach	Upregulation via gene replacement and ASO strategies.				
Clinical Criteria					
Natural History Data	Sufficient natural history data of the disease available,				
Symptoms + Outcome measures	LoF variants cause an early-onset and rapidly progressive form of Stargardt disease (STGD1). The disease is progressive, with varying severity. ¹² Typically, it presents with rapid central visual impairment and progressive bilateral atrophy of the foveal retinal pigment epithelium. ¹³ It can be detected in late childhood or early adulthood, but sometimes vision loss may not be noticed until later in adulthood. ¹²				

	Clinical outcome measures will be the slowing down or halt of disease progression and can be measured as vision loss over time.
Progression rate + Therapeutic Window	The disease is progressive, and the therapeutic window depends on the severity of the disease, usually multiple years to decades if slowly progressive.
Affected tissue + Target tissues	Retinal disease, targeting locally possible
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk	Given the localized affected tissue on the possibility to target the tissue locally, there is a low systemic risk. An additional advantage is that therapy can be tested on one eye first, and disease progression be compared with the second eye.
Practical Criteria	
Available targeted therapies	No market approved therapies are available. However, different types of therapies have been tested pre-clinically and clinically. ASO approaches may offer a viable option for certain variants. ^{14,15} Other strategies being considered include RNA exon editors and dual AAV vectors to deliver the complete human <i>ABCA4</i> gene. ^{16,17}
Preclinical development necessities	Cellular models – retinal organoids – are available to test therapies.
Individualized vs. Generalized	Generalized therapeutic approach for gene replacement and other therapies for common variants. Private variants can also be considered for an individualized approach as long as no generalized approaches are market approved.
Outcome	
The <i>ABCA4</i> gene is a strong candidate for gene therapy. Restoring even partial protein expression could have a substantial therapeutic benefit by slowing or preventing photoreceptor loss. The immune-privileged status of the eye and its relative isolation from systemic circulation make it particularly well suited for localized gene delivery. ¹⁵	

SCN2A-associated early infantile epilepsy

SCN2A is given as an example because of the ongoing clinical trials and available therapies for GOF variants, and the discussions around the association with haploinsufficiency of *SCN2A*. Despite initial worries that downregulation of *SCN2A* would lead to difficulties, so far, the therapeutic interventions have shown clinical success.

Disease	Early infantile epilepsy	OMIM	# 613721	Orphanet	1934
Gene	<i>SCN2A</i>	GeneReviews	n/a		
Molecular Criteria					
Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)	<i>De novo</i> autosomal dominant GoF variants in the <i>SCN2A</i> gene are associated with early infantile epilepsy with onset before 3 months of age. These variants are associated with a variable phenotype and a generally good response to sodium channel blockers. ^{18,19}				

Inheritance + Pathomechanism	Autosomal dominant GoF variants
Dosage sensitivity	<i>SCN2A</i> is associated with haploinsufficiency. AD LoF variants lead to later-onset epilepsies or autism spectrum disorder and intellectual disability without seizures. Generally, the LoF variants lead to a milder phenotype compared to the GoF variants.
Therapeutic Approach	The therapeutic approach is downregulation; albeit caution should be taken to not downregulate the gene product too much.
Clinical Criteria	
Natural History Data	There are ample case reports available as well as natural history data. Given the variability in clinical presentation, understanding the clinical presentation of a given GoF variant is recommended.
Symptoms + Outcome measures	GoF variants cause early infantile epilepsies that present with variable severity but are associated with seizure onset usually before 3 months of age. There is a good response to sodium channel blockers reported. Clinical outcome measures will be the reduction in seizure frequency.
Progression rate + Therapeutic Window	There is a huge variability in clinical presentations, with some cases getting worse while others show improvement over time. No clear therapeutic window has yet been defined. Yet, given the early onset of the disease and severe epilepsy, early intervention is recommended.
Affected tissue + Target tissues	Brain
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk	The benefit-risk evaluation should be made as a case-by-case assessment given the variability in presentation. Severe GoF cases can benefit from genetic intervention whereas for milder cases, this should be discussed with caution.
Practical Criteria	
Available targeted therapies	While no genetic therapy has yet been market-approved, several genetic therapies have been clinically delivered in trial settings. Interestingly, independently developed allele-selective as well as non-allele-selective ASOs have both been clinically administered. ²⁰⁻²³
Preclinical development necessities	A multitude of <i>in vivo</i> and <i>in vitro</i> models is available. Caution should be taken that the model recapitulates the GoF phenotype. ^{24,25} (40884529)
Individualized vs. Generalized	Generalized therapy development as knockdown approaches, especially non-allele-selective, will be applicable to all individuals diagnosed with a GoF variant.
Outcome	
<i>SCN2A</i> -associated early infantile epilepsy is generally an interesting target for genetic intervention. Notably, therapeutic intervention should be discussed in respect to the clinical presentation of each individual. The challenge will be to assess whether the identified (likely) pathogenic variants are indeed GoF variants to justify treatment.	

CSPSD – Cataracts, spastic paraparesis, and speech delay

FAR1-associated CSPSD is included in this overview to highlight a disorder for which a therapeutic intervention would be clinically feasible as well as suitable on a molecular level. No clinical trials or pre-clinical proof-of-concept have yet been reported.

Disease	CSPSD	OMIM	# 619338	Orphanet	615938
Gene	<i>FAR1</i>	GeneReviews	n/a		

Molecular Criteria	
Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)	CSPSD is caused by <i>de novo</i> variants in <i>FAR1</i> inherited in an autosomal dominant manner. CSPSD leads to progressive neurological symptoms, including a movement disorder, seizures, and speech and cognitive delay. <i>FAR1</i> , peroxisomal fatty acyl-CoA reductase 1, is considered to be the rate-limiting enzyme in ether (phospho)lipid biosynthesis. <i>De novo</i> pathogenic variants in <i>FAR1</i> disturb a negative feedback regulation resulting in increased <i>FAR1</i> protein levels and activity, leading to elevated plasmalogen levels ultimately causing disease. All except one individual described in the literature to-date have a missense variant affecting the same amino acid, albeit different amino acid changes due to different nucleotide changes. ^{26,27}
Inheritance + Pathomechanism	Autosomal dominant GoF variants
Dosage sensitivity	No haploinsufficiency. Carriers of heterozygous LoF variants are unaffected. There is a second, autosomal recessive disorder associated with LoF variants (Peroxisomal fatty acyl-CoA reductase 1 disorder).
Therapeutic Approach	Downregulation, allele-specific to mimic the status of heterozygous LoF carriers or correction of variants.
Clinical Criteria	
Natural History Data	Limited natural history data is available. Currently, very few case reports have been published. ²⁶⁻²⁹
Symptoms + Outcome measures	Patients present with spastic paraparesis and bilateral congenital or infant-onset cataracts that can be surgically corrected. Patients further present with speech and gross motor developmental delay, including intellectual disability and cognitive delay. Most patients cannot walk without support or are wheelchair bound. Truncal hypotonia has also been described. Some patients develop seizures in the first months of life, which can be controlled with anti-seizure medication. ^{26,27} No clinical outcome measures have yet been defined but could include seizures – should these not be sufficiently controlled – and measurement of spasticity/movement disorder.
Progression rate + Therapeutic Window	Multiple patients have been described to have progressive symptoms, especially an increase in spasticity over time has been noted. No therapeutic window has yet been defined, but the disease has an early-onset in childhood with increase in spasticity also occurring during childhood.
Affected tissue + Target tissues	Central nervous system. One case report also described the involvement of the muscle itself leading to hypotonia.
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk	Given the localized affected tissue on the possibility to target the tissue locally, there is a low systemic effects to be expected.
Practical Criteria	
Available targeted therapies	No targeted therapies are yet available or under development.
Preclinical development necessities	No animal models have yet been reported. Due to the ubiquitous expression of the <i>FAR1</i> gene and the possibility of measuring <i>FAR1</i> levels as well as plasmalogen levels from patient-derived fibroblasts, suitable read-outs are readily available.
Individualized vs. Generalized	Generalized therapeutic applicable as most GoF variants concern the same amino acid, albeit different nucleotide changes. A SNP-specific allele-selective knockdown or correction of this hotspot region can be used to treat most individuals diagnosed with the disorder.
Outcome	

FAR1-associated CSPSD is an interesting disorder to study and consider for genetic therapy development. The molecular cause is easily targetable, and the general target tissue is the central nervous system, albeit extra-neuronal manifestations are still to be investigated further. Since the disorder is progressive early in life, early treatment initiation is recommended.

Osteogenesis Imperfecta

Osteogenesis imperfecta is included as an example to illustrate that despite being a suitable disorder on the molecular level with a targetable pathomechanism, it is currently not feasible to deliver a therapeutic clinically.

Disease	Osteogenesis imperfecta	OMIM	# 166200, # 166210	Orphanet	666
Gene	Multiple	GeneReviews	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1318/		
Molecular Criteria					
Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)	Osteogenesis imperfecta, also known as brittle bone disease, is a group of conditions characterized by bones that break easily. The majority of patients are diagnosed with disease-causing heterozygous variants in the <i>COL1A1</i> or <i>COL1A2</i> genes that mainly occur <i>de novo</i> . The penetrance is 100% with variable expressivity.				
Inheritance + Pathomechanism	Autosomal dominant The functional consequence of the pathogenic variants in the <i>COL1A1/2</i> genes is almost always a dominant-negative effect. However, the loss of one allele can lead to a milder phenotype. ³⁰				
Dosage sensitivity	Haploinsufficiency, but LoF variants are causing a milder phenotype than DN variants.				
Therapeutic Approach	Downregulation of the mutant allele as well as correction of the pathogenic variants are suitable therapeutic strategies. Correction of the pathogenic variants is not a generalized approach.				
Clinical Criteria					
Natural History Data	Natural history data available.				
Symptoms + Outcome measures	Skeletal defects but also patients can further suffer from pulmonary insufficiency, heart failure, and develop dissections of major arteries like the aorta. ³¹ All symptoms are rooted in poorly formed collagen type I affecting connective tissues.				
Progression rate + Therapeutic Window	Disease phenotype progresses over time, and more manifestations develop. There is a variety of symptoms. No definitive therapeutic window can be established.				
Affected tissue + Target tissues	Connective tissue disorder, target tissue is bone.				
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk	Severe and debilitating disease that would benefit from targeted intervention.				
Practical Criteria					
Available targeted therapies	No genetic therapies are available. Many pre-clinical studies are ongoing. ^{32,33} Simultaneously, studies are ongoing to investigate delivery of therapeutic compounds to the bone. ³⁴⁻³⁶				
Preclinical development necessities	Pre-clinical models of osteogenesis imperfecta are available.				

Individualized vs. Generalized	Considered for a generalized approach as a downregulation of the mutant allele can benefit multiple patients if developed SNP-specific.
Outcome	
Not eligible for genetic therapy development at the moment as there are insufficient possibilities to deliver the therapy to the bone in humans.	

Individualized Approaches

NEDAMSS

This disorder is included for consideration as an individualized approach since the severe forms of the disease are highly eligible for therapeutic intervention. This specific example was further chosen as the variants follow a DN pathomechanism. We highlight a case that was treated with a gene replacement therapy.

Disease	NEDAMSS	OMIM	# 611720	Orphanet	597623
Gene	<i>IRF2BPL</i>	GeneReviews	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK609461/		
Molecular Criteria					
Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)	Caused by truncating and missense variants in <i>IRF2BPL</i> . The disease is well understood, with the genomic location of the pathogenic variant influencing disease severity. The penetrance appears to be high; however, there is interfamilial variability in the age of onset and clinical features.				
Inheritance + Pathomechanism	Autosomal Dominant DN, nonsense variants in the gene leading to early truncation cause a dominant negative effect. ³⁷				
Dosage sensitivity	The ClinGen consortium found little evidence of haploinsufficiency and no evidence of triplosensitivity, pLI of <i>IRF2BPL</i> is 0.91.				
Therapeutic Approach	Allele selective knockdown (gapmer or siRNA) or upregulation of the wildtype copy of the gene via ASOs or gene replacement are potential therapeutic strategies for these nonsense variants. Correction via gene editing is also a possibility for individual cases if delivery to the target tissue is possible.				
Clinical Criteria					
Natural History Data	Lack of natural history data, only a few case reports are available.				
Symptoms + Outcome measures	Symptoms are a mild to profound developmental delay, sometimes with regression, intellectual disability, seizures, movement disorders and autism spectrum disorder. Interestingly, the type of genetic variant influences the phenotype. Patients carrying <i>de novo</i> nonsense variants resulting in a premature stop codon displaying severe clinical presentation with neurodevelopmental regression, hypotonia, progressive ataxia, seizures, and a lack of coordination. Whereas patients diagnosed with missense variants exhibit a milder phenotype with leading symptoms being global developmental delay and seizures. ³⁸ A very severe phenotype with patients presenting with progressive myoclonus epilepsy has also recently been described. ³⁹ Outcome measures could include developmental improvement, reduction or halt in disease progression and seizure control/reduction.				
Progression rate + Therapeutic Window	The more severe end of the phenotypic spectrum is highly progressive. The exact therapeutic window is unclear; however, it could depend on developmental milestones.				

Affected tissue + Target tissues	The affected tissue and target tissue are the central nervous system.
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk	The severe epilepsy and progressive forms of the disease can benefit from genetic therapy. For milder forms, a different benefit-risk analysis will have to be made.
Practical Criteria	
Available targeted therapies	There are currently no targeted therapies market approved. An individual has recently been dosed with a gene replacement therapy.
Preclinical development necessities	There is a mouse model available.
Individualized vs. Generalized	Due to the expressivity variability and the low number of patients, an individualized approach is recommended. However, gene replacement therapy and knockdown of the mutant allele (SNP-specific) can be applicable to multiple patients.
Outcome	
Eligibility depends on the disease severity, the age, and the therapeutic window of opportunity of a patient who would receive genetic therapy. Highly progressive forms of the disease are eligible for genetic therapy, and there is the possibility of delivering genetic therapies to the target tissue. Currently, there is one patient who has recently received gene replacement therapy. ⁴⁰	

Niemann Pick Disease type C

Niemann Pick disease is discussed as one of the autosomal-recessive metabolic diseases suitable for a genetic intervention on a molecular and phenotypic level. We highlight a case for which an individualized genetic therapy has recently been developed.

Disease	Niemann Pick Disease type C	OMIM	# 257220	Orphanet	646
Gene	<i>NPC1</i>	GeneReviews	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1296/		
Molecular Criteria					
Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)	Autosomal recessive variants in the <i>NPC1</i> gene cause Niemann-Pick disease type C, a slowly progressive lysosomal storage disorder. Niemann Pick type C can also be caused by variants in <i>NPC2</i> . Assessments are made for <i>NPC1</i> . There is a clear gene-disease association. Niemann-Pick type C leads to neuronal loss, particularly of the Purkinje cells in the cerebellum. ⁴¹				
Inheritance + Pathomechanism	Autosomal recessive LoF				
Dosage sensitivity	The variants are biallelic LoF, and no triplosensitivity has been reported for the <i>NPC1</i> gene.				
Therapeutic Approach	The most suitable therapeutic strategy is an upregulation of the gene product via a gene replacement, ASOs for upregulation or splice correction (where applicable to individual variants).				
Clinical Criteria					
Natural History Data	There is sufficient natural history data available to provide understanding of clinical presentation and progression. The disease can be distinguished into four major groups depending on the onset of neurological symptoms (early infantile, late infantile, juvenile, and adult).				
Symptoms + Outcome measures	Niemann-Pick type C is a severe neurological disorder characterized by developmental delay, mental deterioration, loss of speech, dementia, cerebellar ataxia, spasticity, behavioral problems, including psychosis.				

Progression rate + Therapeutic Window	An early onset is associated with faster disease progression and premature death. Death most often occurs in late teenage years or young adolescence. Thus, depending on the onset of symptoms, the therapeutic window varies (difference in progression rates).
Affected tissue + Target tissues	Brain.
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk	Therapeutic benefit and risk assessments depend highly on the individual and disease onset. For severe and progressive cases, a substantial therapeutic benefit is expected.
Practical Criteria	
Available therapies	There are a few approved disease modifying small molecule drugs that demonstrated to slow the neurological progression; however, no targeted genetic therapies are market approved. ⁴² A single individual with NPC1 has recently been dosed for the first time with an ASO. ⁴³
Preclinical development necessities	Different pre-clinical models are available. ⁴⁴
Individualized vs. Generalized	NPC1 is considered for individualized genetic therapy development due to the low patient numbers and depending on the individual progression rate.
Outcome	
NPC1 is a suitable therapeutic candidate, as delivery to the central nervous system is possible. For individualized therapy development, one has to understand the individual's disease progression to determine the therapeutic window and also the potential clinical benefit for a given patient. The individual's genetic variant will also determine what therapeutic strategy, ASOs, gene replacement, etc., is most suitable. However, caution should be taken as Niemann-Pick type C is one of the few lysosomal storage diseases (LSD) caused by variants in a gene encoding a protein of the lysosomal membrane (with 7 transmembrane domains). This might be a limitation for a genetic therapy approach since cross-correction is not possible, and clinical benefits might thus be limited.	

GM1 Gangliosidosis

GM1 Gangliosidosis, another inborn error of metabolism, is discussed as there is no genetic therapy approved disease-modifying therapy on the market, but the clinical presentation makes it an interesting candidate to consider, especially for individualized approaches due to the different clinical presentations.

Disease	GM1 Gangliosidosis	OMIM	# 230500	Orphanet	354
Gene	<i>GLB1</i>	GeneReviews	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK164500/		
Molecular Criteria					
Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)	GM1 gangliosidosis is an autosomal recessive lysosomal storage disorder caused by biallelic variants (homozygous and compound heterozygous) in the gene encoding beta-galactosidase-1 (GLB1). There is a clear gene-disease association. The disease is characterized by accumulation of ganglioside substrates in lysosomes. ⁴⁵				
Inheritance + Pathomechanism	Autosomal recessive LoF				
Dosage sensitivity	None reported				
Therapeutic Approach	Upregulation via gene replacement, but also correction via ASO and gene editing approaches for individual variants.				

Clinical Criteria	
Natural History Data	Sufficient natural history data available.
Symptoms + Outcome measures	Clinically, the different types of GM1 gangliosidosis can be distinguished. The infantile form (type 1) is characterized by rapid psychomotor deterioration with onset within 6 months of birth, generalized central nervous system involvement, hepatosplenomegaly, facial dysmorphism, macular cherry-red spots, skeletal dysplasia, and early death. The late-infantile/juvenile type 2 is characterized by central nervous system involvement with psychomotor deterioration, seizures, localized skeletal involvement, and survival into childhood. The adult/chronic form (type 3) usually develops from 3 to 30 years, and symptoms consist of localized skeletal involvement and localized central nervous system involvement, such as dystonia or gait or speech disturbance. There is a correlation between residual enzyme activity and disease severity. Clinical outcome measures will depend on disease type.
Progression rate + Therapeutic Window	The disease is progressive, but progression and therapeutic window depend on the type of GM1 Gangliosidosis present in the individual patient
Affected tissue + Target tissues	Multisystem disorder with severe manifestation in the central nervous system. Target tissue for therapy is the brain. Other manifestations cannot be targeted right now as we cannot deliver therapy to these tissues.
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk	Therapeutic benefit and risk assessments depend highly on the individual and disease type. For severe neurological progressive cases, a substantial therapeutic benefit is to be expected.
Practical Criteria	
Available therapies	No targeted therapies are market approved. A recent phase I/II clinical trial of a gene replacement therapy was reported with limited success. ⁴⁶ Gene editing approaches have been studied pre-clinically and found to be successful. ⁴⁷
Preclinical development necessities	Animal models as well as human-derived cerebral organoids are available.
Individualized vs. Generalized	Considered for individualized approaches.
Outcome	
Interesting target for genetic therapy development but suitability will highly depend on the individual and the individual's presentation, especially severity of extraneuronal manifestations, progression rate and therapeutic window have to be considered carefully before any individualized genetic therapy development can commence. Extraneuronal manifestations can currently not be targeted due to limitations in delivery possibilities.	

Leigh syndrome, Mitochondrial complex I deficiency, nuclear type 34

One form of Leigh syndrome is presented here as it is an interesting disorder to consider for individualized therapeutic development, given the clinical presentation of the disease and associated target tissues, especially the brain and eye.

Disease	Leigh syndrome	OMIM	# 618776	Orphanet	2609
Gene	<i>NDUFAF8</i>	GeneReviews	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK320989/		
Molecular Criteria					

Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)	Bi-allelic LoF variants (homozygous or compound heterozygous) in <i>NDUFAF8</i> are one cause of Leigh syndrome, a commonly described neurological phenotype in pediatric mitochondrial disorders. <i>NDUFAF8</i> LoF variants lead to an isolated complex I deficiency. The extent of the defect and severity of the phenotype are dependent on the variant and the left-over complex I function. There is a clear gene-disease association. ⁴⁸
Inheritance + Pathomechanism	Autosomal recessive LoF
Dosage sensitivity	None reported.
Therapeutic Approach	Upregulation via gene replacement, but also correction via ASO and gene editing approaches for individual variants.
Clinical Criteria	
Natural History Data	There is good natural history data available on Leigh syndrome in general. However, for the individual causes and genes associated with Leigh syndrome, like <i>NDUFAF8</i> , limited case reports have been published. ⁴⁸
Symptoms + Outcome measures	Leigh syndrome is generally a neurodegenerative condition. Onset of the disorder is usually in infancy or early childhood. Individuals present with a variety of neurological symptoms like infantile spasms, delayed developmental milestones and progressive loss of (neuro-)developmental skills and cognitive function. On MRI, typical findings include lesions in the basal ganglia, thalamus and brainstem symmetrical lesions in the basal ganglia, thalamus, and brainstem, and is associated with a loss of acquired cognitive, visual, and motor skills. Clinical outcome measures could focus around the regression and cognitive decline and measurement of developmental milestones.
Progression rate + Therapeutic Window	The disease is progressive. With onset in early childhood and the reported loss of milestones, including premature death, the therapeutic window is in the early years of life.
Affected tissue + Target tissues	Central nervous system, including retina.
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk	Therapeutic benefit and risk assessments depend highly on the individual as different variants lead to different amounts of left-over enzymatic function which will determine disease presentation and progression and also define the benefit-risk ratio.
Practical Criteria	
Available therapies	No targeted therapies are market approved.
Preclinical development necessities	Limited information yet available on suitable animal and cell models. However, the enzymatic activity of complex I can be measured in fibroblasts and other patient-derived cells.
Individualized vs. Generalized	Considered for individualized approaches given the limited number of reported cases to date and the variable phenotypic presentation.
Outcome	
Interesting target for genetic therapy development but suitability will highly depend on the individual and the individual's presentation, which will be dependent on left-over function of the protein and with that mitochondrial complex I. Patients with leaky variants, especially those affecting splicing via deep-intronic variants correctable via ASOs, have been reported to show a milder and slower progressive phenotype. Given that these individuals progress slower and show a milder phenotype makes this disorder even more suitable as it is indirect evidence that even a slight increase in complex I deficiency can slow down the disease progression.	

Lissencephaly 1

Lissencephaly is included as it is a disorder with a broad clinical presentation. We highlight that prenatal defects cannot be corrected or reversed with postnatal genetic intervention.

Disease	Lissencephaly 1	OMIM	# 607432	Orphanet	95232
Gene	<i>PAFAH1B1</i>	GeneReviews	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK5189/		
Molecular Criteria					
Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)	Lissencephaly, meaning smooth brain, is a disorder associated with different genetic defects. <i>De novo</i> heterozygous LoF variants in <i>PAFAH1B1</i> are one cause of this phenotypic spectrum. The clinical manifestation of the disorder originates from neuronal migration defects occurring at 9 to 13 weeks' gestation. The variants in <i>PAFAH1B1</i> exhibit high penetrance but variable expressivity. Depending on the nature and location of the (likely) pathogenic variant, the clinical presentation can range from the profound Miller-Dieker syndrome to milder phenotypes like the isolated lissencephaly sequence (ILS) or subcortical band heterotopia (SBH). ^{49,50}				
Inheritance + Pathomechanism	Autosomal dominant LoF variants, often larger deletions				
Dosage sensitivity	Known haploinsufficiency. Potential triplosensitivity as overexpression of LIS1 in mice leads to brain defects and duplications of the 17p13.3 region, which contains <i>PAFAH1B1</i> (LIS1), are associated with neurodevelopmental issues, including autism, learning disabilities, and microcephaly. ⁵¹				
Therapeutic Approach	Upregulation via gene replacement or ASO. Since most patients show deletions in the gene, correction via editing is not possible at the moment.				
Clinical Criteria					
Natural History Data	Sufficient natural history data of the disease available,				
Symptoms + Outcome measures	Lissencephaly is characterized typical neuroimaging findings that include abnormally broad or absent cerebral gyri. Further, an abnormally thick and poorly organized cerebral cortex can be observed, including diffuse neuronal heterotopia, overall leading to a smooth brain surface. ⁵² The affected individuals present with hypotonia, feeding difficulties and poor control of the head. Infants further show poor visual tracking and limited response to sounds. They can also develop spasticity that increases in severity over time. Seizures occur in the majority of affected individuals, which are often drug-resistant. Even with good seizure control, individuals do not reach developmental levels beyond those of three to five months. ⁵²				
Progression rate + Therapeutic Window	The disorder has been described to be non-progressive with defects being present at birth. The manifestation of the disorder occurs early in the gestational development. The therapeutic window would thus be during early pregnancy.				
Affected tissue + Target tissues	Central nervous system.				
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk	This is a severely debilitating disorder.				
Practical Criteria					
Available targeted therapies	No market approved targeted therapies are available.				

Preclinical development necessities	Different animal models and iPSC-derived organoid models are available. ⁵³
Individualized vs. Generalized	This disorder can be assessed for individual or generalized approaches.
Outcome	
Since lissencephaly presents with major changes to the brain anatomy at birth, the disorder is not suitable target for a genetic intervention as the defects cannot be corrected postnatally. Reversal of symptoms is highly unlikely as neuronal migration defects occur early during development at the age of 9 – 13 weeks' gestation.	

Marfan syndrome

Marfan syndrome is listed in this overview to illustrate a disorder that has a broad clinical presentation and can thus be considered for individual approaches. We highlight that Marfan syndrome can currently not be targeted due to limitations in delivery options to the target tissue.

Disease	Marfan syndrome	OMIM	# 154700	Orphanet	558
Gene	<i>FBN1</i>	GeneReviews	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1335/		
Molecular Criteria					
Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)	Caused by pathogenic variants in <i>FBN1</i> . Variable expressivity but complete penetrance, ⁵⁴ highly variable phenotype between patients.				
Inheritance + Pathomechanism	Autosomal dominant LoF				
Dosage sensitivity	Haploinsufficient. No evidence for triplosensitivity.				
Therapeutic Approach	Upregulation				
Clinical Criteria					
Natural History Data	Despite its clinical variability, there is extensive natural history data available on the disease and the different manifestations.				
Symptoms + Outcome measures	Multi systemic disorder of the connective tissue presenting with a broad phenotypic spectrum. Affected organs: skeletal, muscular, cardiovascular system, ocular system, mild to progressive scoliosis. It is not easy to define clear outcome measures other than prevention of acute manifestations like, for example: retinal detachment, glaucoma, early cataracts, ectopia lentis. Major morbidity and early mortality related to the cardiovascular system.				
Progression rate + Therapeutic Window	Progression rate and therapeutic window are highly variable as individuals can present with very mild to severe and rapidly progressive multisystem disorder.				
Affected tissue + Target tissues	Multisystem disorder with main target tissue being the connective tissue.				
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk	Therapeutic benefit and risk assessments depend highly on the individual. In very severe and progressive cases, an experimental genetic intervention can be justified.				
Practical Criteria					
Available targeted therapies	No disease-modifying treatments are available. Current clinical care focuses on symptom management and regular surveillance.				

Preclinical development necessities	Animal models as well as human stem cell models for the disease are available.
Individualized vs. Generalized	Given the high phenotypic variability, a genetic intervention might not be necessary for every individual, especially considering the risks of a genetic intervention. Thus, therapeutic eligibility can be assessed on an individual basis.
Outcome	
Currently not eligible. This is a multisystem disorder with the main target tissue being the connective tissue. There has not yet been any in-human proof-of-concept that this tissue can be reached sufficiently and systemically with current delivery methods of genetic therapies.	

Dejerine-Sottas disease

(Charcot-Marie-Tooth Disease Type 3, Hereditary Motor and Sensory Neuropathy Type III)

Dejerine-Sottas disease is included to highlight a disorder that from its initial clinical presentation looks like a good candidate given the neurological phenotype, but upon closer examination is a challenging target since the target tissue is the peripheral nervous system that would have to be reached with a systemic delivery.

Disease	Dejerine-Sottas disease	OMIM	# 145900	Orphanet	64748
Gene	<i>PMP22</i>	GeneReviews	n/a		
Molecular Criteria					
Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)	Pathogenic monoallelic and biallelic variants in the <i>PMP22</i> gene can cause Dejerine-Sottas syndrome. ⁵⁵ This neuropathy is a demyelinating peripheral neuropathy and is characterized by a highly variable clinical expressivity. Onset can reach from infancy to adulthood. The syndrome has been associated with autosomal dominant or recessive inheritance. ⁵⁶ The disease is characterized by a loss of Schwann cells due to apoptosis which can result from a variety of <i>PMP22</i> variants, including duplications, deletions, and point mutations. ⁵⁷				
Inheritance + Pathomechanism	Autosomal recessive and autosomal dominant LoF variants, GoF variants including 17p11.2 duplication (duplication of <i>PMP22</i>)				
Dosage sensitivity	Haploinsufficiency in AD, but carriers of LoF variants associated with the AR phenotype present without a clinical phenotype. Given that GoF and LoF variants can cause the disease is indicative that <i>PMP22</i> levels have to be tightly regulated. Indeed, pathogenic variants (LoF, GoF) in <i>PMP22</i> account for the majority of all inherited peripheral neuropathies. ⁵⁷				
Therapeutic Approach	Downregulation of the GoF variants/duplication Upregulation or correction with ASO/editing technologies for the LoF variants				
Clinical Criteria					
Natural History Data	The syndrome can be caused by pathogenic variants in multiple genes. Case reports of affected individuals or groups of patients are available. ⁵⁸				
Symptoms + Outcome measures	This demyelinating peripheral neuropathy presents with moderate to severe weakness of the lower and upper extremities and a loss of sensation. As the disease progresses, a loss of muscle and a reduction in muscle tone become evident. Individuals further present with delayed motor development due to the				

	<p>sensory impairments. A hallmark feature are the severely reduced nerve conduction velocities, which may present as peripheral areflexia.</p> <p>Affected individuals further have difficulties walking and can present with ataxia, they may end up in a wheelchair. Patients may also present with scoliosis, foot deformities and clawed hands.⁵⁸</p>
Progression rate + Therapeutic Window	<p>The disorder is progressive. Usually, progression is slow into teenage years but can accelerate thereafter and cause severe disabilities.</p> <p>Given the limited natural history data and variable expressivity, a clear therapeutic window has not yet been defined. However, the initial slow progression can allow for individualized therapy development.</p>
Affected tissue + Target tissues	Peripheral nervous system, especially Schwann cells.
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk	The severely debilitating forms of the disease justify the risks associated with a genetic intervention.
Practical Criteria	
Available targeted therapies	No disease-modifying therapies are currently available.
Preclinical development necessities	A mouse model is available. Human and mouse-derived Schwann cell models are also available.
Individualized vs. Generalized	Due to the limited patient numbers, the highly variable expressivity and the two different inheritance patterns, individual therapeutic approaches are suitable as a genetic therapy might not be applicable to all that are affected by the disease.
Outcome	
<p>Pathogenic variants in <i>PMP22</i> are difficult to assess. Due to the different pathomechanisms causative of the disease, the different types of genetic variants, and the highly variable clinical phenotype, as well as the overlap of symptoms in Dejerine-Sottas disease with its allelic disorders, each case should be evaluated carefully. The severe, progressive phenotype is generally an interesting target for a therapeutic development but since the mainly affected cell type are the Schwann cells, one needs to bear in mind that this cell type can currently not be reached with an intrathecal injection and will require systemic administration. While pre-clinical studies to achieve delivering to Schwann cells are ongoing, even targeting <i>PMP22</i>;⁵⁹ this approach has not yet been implemented in a clinical setting.</p>	

Template

Disease	OMIM	Orphanet
Gene	GeneReviews	
Molecular Criteria		
Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)		
Inheritance + Pathomechanism		
Dosage sensitivity		
Therapeutic Approach		
Clinical Criteria		
Natural History Data		
Symptoms + Outcome measures		
Progression rate + Therapeutic Window		
Affected tissue + Target tissues		
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk		
Practical Criteria		
Available targeted therapies		
Preclinical development necessities		
Individualized vs. Generalized		
Outcome		

References

1. Prior TW, Leach ME, Finanger EL. Spinal Muscular Atrophy. 1993;doi:NBK1352
2. Van Alstyne M, Tattoli I, Delestree N, et al. Gain of toxic function by long-term AAV9-mediated SMN overexpression in the sensorimotor circuit. *Nat Neurosci*. Jul 2021;24(7):930-940. doi:10.1038/s41593-021-00827-3
3. Elamin M, Dumarchey A, Stoddard C, et al. The role of UBE3A in the autism and epilepsy-related Dup15q syndrome using patient-derived, CRISPR-corrected neurons. *Stem Cell Reports*. Apr 11 2023;18(4):884-898. doi:10.1016/j.stemcr.2023.02.002
4. Hipp JF, Bacino CA, Bird LM, et al. The UBE3A-ATS antisense oligonucleotide rugonersen in children with Angelman syndrome: a phase 1 trial. *Nat Med*. Sep 2025;31(9):2936-2945. doi:10.1038/s41591-025-03784-7
5. Silva-Santos S, van Woerden GM, Bruinsma CF, et al. Ube3a reinstatement identifies distinct developmental windows in a murine Angelman syndrome model. *J Clin Invest*. May 2015;125(5):2069-76. doi:10.1172/JCI80554
6. Brunklaus A, Brunger T, Feng T, et al. The gain of function SCN1A disorder spectrum: novel epilepsy phenotypes and therapeutic implications. *Brain*. Nov 21 2022;145(11):3816-3831. doi:10.1093/brain/awac210
7. Han Z, Chen C, Christiansen A, et al. Antisense oligonucleotides increase Scn1a expression and reduce seizures and SUDEP incidence in a mouse model of Dravet syndrome. *Sci Transl Med*. Aug 26 2020;12(558)doi:10.1126/scitranslmed.aaz6100
8. Mich JK, Ryu J, Wei AD, et al. Interneuron-specific dual-AAV SCN1A gene replacement corrects epileptic phenotypes in mouse models of Dravet syndrome. *Sci Transl Med*. Mar 19 2025;17(790):eadn5603. doi:10.1126/scitranslmed.adn5603
9. Clinical Trials of Zorevunersen. National Library of Medicine. Accessed February 25, 2026. <https://www.clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06872125>
10. Griffin A, Hamling KR, Hong S, Anvar M, Lee LP, Baraban SC. Preclinical Animal Models for Dravet Syndrome: Seizure Phenotypes, Comorbidities and Drug Screening. *Front Pharmacol*. 2018;9:573. doi:10.3389/fphar.2018.00573
11. Kohli P, Tripathy K, Kaur K. Stargardt Disease. Jan 2025;doi:NBK587351
12. Al-Khuzaei S, Broadgate S, Foster CR, et al. An Overview of the Genetics of ABCA4 Retinopathies, an Evolving Story. *Genes (Basel)*. Aug 13 2021;12(8)doi:10.3390/genes12081241
13. Lee W, Zernant J, Nagasaki T, et al. Cis-acting modifiers in the ABCA4 locus contribute to the penetrance of the major disease-causing variant in Stargardt disease. *Hum Mol Genet*. Jun 26 2021;30(14):1293-1304. doi:10.1093/hmg/ddab122
14. Kaltak M, Blanco-Garavito R, Molday LL, et al. Stargardt disease-associated in-frame ABCA4 exon 17 skipping results in significant ABCA4 function. *J Transl Med*. Aug 16 2023;21(1):546. doi:10.1186/s12967-023-04406-x
15. Kaltak M, de Bruijn P, Piccolo D, et al. Antisense oligonucleotide therapy corrects splicing in the common Stargardt disease type 1-causing variant ABCA4 c.5461-10T>C. *Mol Ther Nucleic Acids*. Mar 14 2023;31:674-688. doi:10.1016/j.omtn.2023.02.020
16. Clinical Trials of ACDN-01. National Library of Medicine. Accessed February 25, 2026. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06467344>
17. Clinical Trials of VG801. National Library of Medicine. Accessed February 25, 2026. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT07002398>
18. Wolff M, Johannesen KM, Hedrich UBS, et al. Genetic and phenotypic heterogeneity suggest therapeutic implications in SCN2A-related disorders. *Brain*. May 1 2017;140(5):1316-1336. doi:10.1093/brain/awx054

19. Berecki G, Howell KB, Heighway J, et al. Functional correlates of clinical phenotype and severity in recurrent SCN2A variants. *Commun Biol*. May 30 2022;5(1):515. doi:10.1038/s42003-022-03454-1
20. Kim-McManus O, Goddard P, Olsson S, et al. Scaling haplospecific antisense oligonucleotides from N-of-1 to broad use in genetic disease populations by diplotyping. *medRxiv*. 2026:2026.01.28.26345012. doi:10.64898/2026.01.28.26345012
21. Clinical Trial of nL-SCN2A-002. National Library of Medicine. Accessed May 8, 2026. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06314490>
22. Clinical trial of Elsunersen. National Library of Medicine. Accessed May 8, 2026. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT07019922>
23. Wagner M, Berecki G, Fazeli W, et al. Antisense oligonucleotide treatment in a preterm infant with early-onset SCN2A developmental and epileptic encephalopathy. *Nat Med*. Jul 2025;31(7):2174-2178. doi:10.1038/s41591-025-03656-0
24. Mao M, Mattei C, Rollo B, et al. Distinctive In Vitro Phenotypes in iPSC-Derived Neurons From Patients With Gain- and Loss-of-Function SCN2A Developmental and Epileptic Encephalopathy. *J Neurosci*. Feb 21 2024;44(8)doi:10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0692-23.2023
25. Scott KEJ, Hermosillo Arrieta MF, Williams AJ. Deciphering SCN2A: A comprehensive review of rodent models of Scn2a dysfunction. *Epilepsia*. Dec 2025;66(12):4624-4638. doi:10.1111/epi.18615
26. Ferdinandusse S, McWalter K, Te Brinke H, et al. An autosomal dominant neurological disorder caused by de novo variants in FAR1 resulting in uncontrolled synthesis of ether lipids. *Genet Med*. Apr 2021;23(4):740-750. doi:10.1038/s41436-020-01027-3
27. Westenberger A, Ruiz-Herrera A, Bozdogan S, et al. Spectrum of FAR1 (Fatty Acyl-CoA Reductase 1) Variants and Related Neurological Conditions. *Mov Disord*. Mar 2023;38(3):502-504. doi:10.1002/mds.29323
28. Della Marina A, Hentschel A, Stenzel M, et al. Lipid and protein imbalances in muscle of a FAR1-patient with a heterozygous de novo variant. *J Neuropathol Exp Neurol*. Nov 1 2024;83(11):979-983. doi:10.1093/jnen/nlae071
29. Shambhavi A, Moirangthem A, Pandey M, S RP. Complex Hereditary Spastic Paraparesis Caused by de novo p.Arg480Ser in FAR1. *Indian J Pediatr*. Aug 2024;91(8):839-841. doi:10.1007/s12098-023-04652-3
30. van Dijk FS, Huizer M, Kariminejad A, et al. Complete COL1A1 allele deletions in osteogenesis imperfecta. *Genet Med*. Nov 2010;12(11):736-41. doi:10.1097/GIM.0b013e3181f01617
31. Tosi LL, Oetgen ME, Floor MK, et al. Initial report of the osteogenesis imperfecta adult natural history initiative. *Orphanet J Rare Dis*. Nov 14 2015;10:146. doi:10.1186/s13023-015-0362-2
32. Yang YS, Sato T, Chaugule S, et al. AAV-based gene editing of type 1 collagen mutation to treat osteogenesis imperfecta. *Mol Ther Nucleic Acids*. Mar 12 2024;35(1):102111. doi:10.1016/j.omtn.2023.102111
33. Schindeler A, Lee LR, O'Donohue AK, Ginn SL, Munns CF. Curative Cell and Gene Therapy for Osteogenesis Imperfecta. *J Bone Miner Res*. May 2022;37(5):826-836. doi:10.1002/jbmr.4549
34. Lin C, Greenblatt MB, Gao G, Shim JH. Development of AAV-Mediated Gene Therapy Approaches to Treat Skeletal Diseases. *Hum Gene Ther*. May 2024;35(9-10):317-328. doi:10.1089/hum.2024.022
35. Lin C, Yang YS, Ma H, et al. Engineering a targeted and safe bone anabolic gene therapy to treat osteoporosis in alveolar bone loss. *Mol Ther*. Sep 4 2024;32(9):3080-3100. doi:10.1016/j.ymthe.2024.06.036

36. Wu Y, Sun B, Tang Y, et al. Bone targeted nano-drug and nano-delivery. *Bone Res.* Sep 4 2024;12(1):51. doi:10.1038/s41413-024-00356-2
37. Sinha Ray S, Dutta D, Dennys C, et al. Mechanisms of IRF2BPL-related disorders and identification of a potential therapeutic strategy. *Cell Rep.* Dec 6 2022;41(10):111751. doi:10.1016/j.celrep.2022.111751
38. Marcogliese PC, Shashi V, Spillmann RC, et al. IRF2BPL Is Associated with Neurological Phenotypes. *Am J Hum Genet.* Aug 2 2018;103(2):245-260. doi:10.1016/j.ajhg.2018.07.006
39. Gardella E, Michelucci R, Christensen HM, et al. IRF2BPL as a novel causative gene for progressive myoclonus epilepsy. *Epilepsia.* Aug 2023;64(8):e170-e176. doi:10.1111/epi.17634
40. Andelyn Biosciences Applies the AAV Curator® Platform to Deliver Novel Gene Therapy for an Ultra-Rare NEDAMSS Disease Patient 14-Months after Diagnosis. Andelyn Biosciences. Updated May 12, 2025. Accessed February 25, 2026. <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/andelyn-biosciences-applies-the-aaav-curator-platform-to-deliver-novel-gene-therapy-for-an-ultra-rare-nedamss-disease-patient-14-months-after-diagnosis-302451993.html>
41. Higashi Y, Murayama S, Pentchev PG, Suzuki K. Cerebellar degeneration in the Niemann-Pick type C mouse. *Acta Neuropathol.* 1993;85(2):175-84. doi:10.1007/BF00227765
42. New treatment for Niemann-Pick type C disease. European Medicines Agency 2025. <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/news/new-treatment-niemann-pick-type-c-disease>
43. Blackwell M. UK Teenager Receives Personalised Drug for Fatal Niemann-Pick Genetic Condition: Research Breakthrough. Academic Jobs. Accessed February 25, 2026. <https://www.academicjobs.com/research-publication-news/uk-teen-personalised-drug-niemann-pick-fatal-condition-or-research-news-1934>
44. Fog CK, Kirkegaard T. Animal models for Niemann-Pick type C: implications for drug discovery & development. *Expert Opin Drug Discov.* May 2019;14(5):499-509. doi:10.1080/17460441.2019.1588882
45. Regier DS, Tiffit CJ, Rothermel CE. GLB1-Related Disorders. 1993;doi:NBK164500
46. Lewis CJ, D'Souza P, Johnston JM, et al. AAV9 Gene Therapy in Type II GM1 Gangliosidosis - A Phase 1-2 Trial. *N Engl J Med.* Feb 6 2026;doi:10.1056/NEJMoa2510935
47. Rha AK, Kan SH, Andrade-Heckman P, Christensen CL, Harb JF, Wang RY. Base editing of the GLB1 gene is therapeutic in GM1 gangliosidosis patient-derived cells. *Mol Genet Metab.* Sep-Oct 2024;143(1-2):108568. doi:10.1016/j.ymgme.2024.108568
48. Alston CL, Veling MT, Heidler J, et al. Pathogenic Bi-allelic Mutations in NDUFAF8 Cause Leigh Syndrome with an Isolated Complex I Deficiency. *Am J Hum Genet.* Jan 2 2020;106(1):92-101. doi:10.1016/j.ajhg.2019.12.001
49. Feng WX, Wang XF, Wu Y, et al. Clinical analysis of PFAFH1B1 gene variants in pediatric patients with epilepsy. *Seizure.* Apr 2024;117:98-104. doi:10.1016/j.seizure.2024.01.020
50. Shi CH, Zhang S, Yang ZH, et al. Identification of a novel PFAFH1B1 missense mutation as a cause of mild lissencephaly with basal ganglia calcification. *Brain Dev.* Jan 2019;41(1):29-35. doi:10.1016/j.braindev.2018.07.009
51. Bi W, Sapir T, Shchelochkov OA, et al. Increased LIS1 expression affects human and mouse brain development. *Nat Genet.* Feb 2009;41(2):168-77. doi:10.1038/ng.302
52. Brock S, Dobyns WB, Jansen A. PFAFH1B1-Related Lissencephaly / Subcortical Band Heterotopia. 1993;doi:NBK5189
53. Zillich L, Gasparotto M, Rossetti AC, et al. Capturing disease severity in LIS1-lissencephaly reveals proteostasis dysregulation in patient-derived forebrain organoids. *Nat Commun.* Oct 13 2025;16(1):9091. doi:10.1038/s41467-025-64980-0
54. von Kodolitsch Y, Robinson PN. Marfan syndrome: an update of genetics, medical and surgical management. *Heart.* Jun 2007;93(6):755-60. doi:10.1136/hrt.2006.098798

55. Roa BB, Dyck PJ, Marks HG, Chance PF, Lupski JR. Dejerine-Sottas syndrome associated with point mutation in the peripheral myelin protein 22 (PMP22) gene. *Nat Genet.* Nov 1993;5(3):269-73. doi:10.1038/ng1193-269
56. Parman Y, Plante-Bordeneuve V, Guiochon-Mantel A, Eraksoy M, Said G. Recessive inheritance of a new point mutation of the PMP22 gene in Dejerine-Sottas disease. *Ann Neurol.* Apr 1999;45(4):518-22. doi:10.1002/1531-8249(199904)45:4<518::aid-ana15>3.0.co;2-u
57. Li J, Parker B, Martyn C, Natarajan C, Guo J. The PMP22 gene and its related diseases. *Mol Neurobiol.* Apr 2013;47(2):673-98. doi:10.1007/s12035-012-8370-x
58. Gabreels-Festen A. Dejerine-Sottas syndrome grown to maturity: overview of genetic and morphological heterogeneity and follow-up of 25 patients. *J Anat.* Apr 2002;200(4):341-56. doi:10.1046/j.1469-7580.2002.00043.x
59. Zhao HT, Damle S, Ikeda-Lee K, et al. PMP22 antisense oligonucleotides reverse Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease type 1A features in rodent models. *J Clin Invest.* Jan 2 2018;128(1):359-368. doi:10.1172/JCI96499